

ASSESSMENT OF THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF THE ENTERPRISE

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Annotation. This article examines the methods of analyzing and evaluating the economic potential of an enterprise and the factors that enhance its efficiency. The main indicators of economic potential and their importance in ensuring the competitiveness of the enterprise are analyzed. The article presents evaluation methods based on financial and economic indicators and discusses their practical application.

Key words: Economic potential of enterprise, analysis, evaluation, financial indicators, competitiveness, efficiency, business analysis, financial stability, investment, enterprise development.

"Organizing economic analysis primarily involves defining its goals and objectives, distributing responsibilities among enterprise departments, implementing internal and external analysis processes, determining methodological approaches and tools, as well as developing, adopting, and implementing measures aimed at increasing the efficiency of the enterprise" (Kocharyan, 2016).

Effectively organizing economic analysis is crucial for centralizing the process of analyzing enterprise activity, directing it toward specific tasks, and substantiating strategic decisions. This process lays the groundwork for "scientifically based management decisions aimed at ensuring the sustainable development of the enterprise" (Nurmanov, 2024).

The methodology of economic analysis refers to a set of specific methods and techniques aimed at studying economic processes and their outcomes. This methodology ensures that the analysis is systematically structured and logically grounded.

"The following technological stages are distinguished in conducting economic analysis:

1. **Defining the object, purpose, and objectives of the analysis and preparing the analysis plan** – allows for planning the analysis, determining strategic directions, and clearly distributing tasks.

2. **Forming a system of indicators representing the analysis object**

– involves selecting accurate, quantifiable, and industry-relevant indicators to evaluate economic processes.

3. **Collecting and preparing necessary data for analysis**

– includes gathering data from reliable sources, thoroughly verifying it, and preparing it for analytical processing.

4. **Comparative analysis of actual economic performance with planned indicators, past data, industry averages, and competitors' results** – performance is assessed using dynamic and comparative analysis methods.

5. **Factor analysis and determining their impact on enterprise performance** – the influence of factors on specific indicators is evaluated on a scientific basis.

6. **Identifying unused and prospective reserves** – determines opportunities for optimizing production and attracting additional resources.

Evaluating the results of economic activity based on factors and reserves, and developing recommendations and measures for their utilization – leads to the formulation of practical suggestions aimed at improving efficiency based on analysis outcomes" (Skobara, 2014).

In identifying the factors influencing enterprise performance, deterministic (factor-based) analysis methods — such as chain substitution, absolute difference, and index evaluation methods — were utilized. These methods enabled the quantitative analysis of the main factors responsible for shaping economic outcomes.

Additionally, to thoroughly examine statistical data, **correlation and regression analysis, as well as trend and dispersion analyses** were employed to assess long-term changes. **Economic-mathematical methods based on modeling** (linear programming, network models, simulation modeling) served as key tools in evaluating the optimal use of enterprise resources.

The research also made extensive use of **management analysis tools**. Specifically:

- **SWOT analysis** helped identify the enterprise's internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats.

- **PEST analysis** was used to examine the political, economic, social, and technological environment.

- **GAP analysis** revealed the discrepancies between planned and actual outcomes.

The application of these methods created a **reliable and analytical foundation** for assessing the enterprise's **production potential and efficiency**.

Proper and relevant evaluation of **production potential** supports effective planning and implementation of both daily operations and long-term development strategies. This, in turn, helps:

- Ensure the enterprise's **current solvency**,
- Strengthen its **competitiveness in the market**, and
- **Stabilize its position** within the industry.

When studying the production potential of agricultural enterprises, it is necessary to employ **special methodological approaches** that take sector-specific characteristics into account.

This includes the calculation of sector-specific analysis indicators. **"Production potential, particularly the efficient and purposeful use of fixed assets and production capacities, directly affects product quality. Moreover, rational use of these resources is a key factor in ensuring the enterprise's competitiveness, strengthening its market position, and achieving economic stability"** (Pardayevich, 2021).

One of the key aspects to consider in organizing economic analysis, particularly in accurately and effectively assessing an enterprise's production potential, is the identification of the "responsible unit" for carrying out this process (Nasibov, 2008).

In practice, such tasks are typically assigned to the enterprise's economic department. In today's rapidly changing market environment, the staff of this department is required to regularly analyze the production capabilities of their enterprises.

Such **systematic analysis contributes to:**

- Creating a continuous information base on how effectively the enterprise's production capacity is being utilized;
- Formulating long-term development strategies and production-financial plans on a scientific basis.

In particular, for **agricultural enterprises**, accurately evaluating and efficiently utilizing production potential requires a deep understanding of the economic essence of this potential. This necessitates the development of **special analytical methods** that take into account sectoral characteristics, the composition of production resources, and their renewability.

According to M. Abdujabborova,

“Production potential is a complex socio-economic system aimed at achieving the maximum production outcome through the most effective use of interrelated production resources” (Abdujabborova, 2023).

This concept includes not only the sum of resources but also their **interactions, management mechanisms, and performance levels**. The improvement of production potential involves the **efficient allocation of resources, their full utilization, and technological renewal**.

There are various **methodological approaches** available for evaluating enterprises’ production potential, including:

1. **Monetary valuation method of potential components** – determining the value expression of each resource that constitutes production potential.
2. **Index method** – assessing the dynamics of potential by comparing changes in various indicators.
3. **Resource-regression method** – identifying the relationship between resources and outcomes using statistical (regression) modeling.
4. **Indicative method** – evaluation and monitoring based on indicators aligned with the strategic goals of the enterprise.
5. **Priority-based resource evaluation method** – assessing potential by prioritizing the most important and influential types of resources.

The use of these methods enables a **comprehensive, systematic, and dynamic evaluation** of an enterprise’s production potential.

Economist **M. Tojiboyeva** proposes the following **set of indicators** to accurately and effectively assess enterprises’ production potential:

- **Potential annual production capacity (in physical units)**: Indicates the maximum output achievable using the enterprise’s existing technology and equipment.
- **Potential annual gross output (in value)**: Reflects the total value of goods, services, and products the enterprise can produce, indicating market potential.
- **Potential value added or conditional net product (in value)**: Shows the new value created during the current production process, essential for evaluating internal efficiency.
- **Potential net annual income**: Represents the net economic value generated by production, reflecting the volume of net output.

• **Potential balance profit (under different pricing strategies):** Assesses total profit under varying market conditions from the enterprise's activities; fundamental for strategic planning.

• **Expected net profit after taxes:** Shows the net profit remaining after all mandatory payments to the state have been made (Tojiboyeva, 2021).

Several key directions are of great importance in analyzing the production potential of an enterprise. These directions make it possible to comprehensively assess the enterprise's economic efficiency, determine the level of resource utilization, and identify potential points for future development.

Firstly, in the analysis of material and technical resources, the structure and current condition of fixed production assets, the degree of modernization of existing equipment and technologies, as well as the return on assets and depreciation rates are studied. This analysis serves as a key criterion for evaluating the efficiency of production means.

Secondly, analyzing labor potential involves determining the number of employees, their professional qualification levels, labor productivity, and the extent of reliance on hired labor. Rational use of labor resources is one of the critical factors in ensuring continuity and efficiency in the production process.

Thirdly, for **agricultural enterprises**, the analysis of land and natural resource utilization is particularly significant. This includes assessing the efficient use of land plots, land productivity, ecological condition, and level of land reclamation (melioration).

Fourthly, in the analysis of production capacity utilization, the gap between the enterprise's full production potential and its actual production volume is identified. The **capacity utilization ratio** and the availability of **reserve capacities** are also taken into account.

Fifthly, within the framework of **economic performance analysis**, indicators such as the gross output volume, net product, added value, total profit, profitability ratios, balance profit, and net income after taxes are analyzed. These metrics play an important role in assessing the financial condition of the enterprise.

Sixthly, the **analysis of innovation potential** focuses on the level of implementation of new technologies, the number of completed scientific and technical developments, and the volume of investments directed toward innovation. This is one of the most critical factors in ensuring competitiveness and sustainable development.

The main goal of economic analysis of production potential is to **study its status, structure, dynamics, and constituent elements**, as well as to **identify the positive and negative factors affecting its implementation**, detect **existing bottlenecks**, and develop **measures to address them**.

To achieve this goal, the following analytical tasks are proposed:

1. Determine the **quantity, structure, and dynamics** of material, labor, and capital resources;
2. Assess the **quality of the resource utilization normalization system** for fixed production and labor resources;
3. Identify **bottlenecks** in specific types of resources or technological processes and develop recommendations to eliminate existing shortcomings;
4. Evaluate the **quality of the production potential planning process**, the validity of planned indicators, and how well they align with actual performance;
5. Identify **inefficient elements of production potential** and prepare proposals for their future utilization;
6. Analyze the **actual level of efficiency in using production and labor resources**, and evaluate how key factors affect production potential indicators;
7. Identify **reserves to increase the efficiency** of production potential utilization (Skrynkovskyy, 2019).

In the **agricultural sector**, one of the most important and unique components of **production potential** is *biological potential*. This refers to the **varieties of agricultural crops and breeds of livestock and poultry** considered as a whole. In other words, **biological potential** means the quantity of agrobiological resources cultivated in a farm and their **genetic, agronomic, and reproductive capabilities**.

Having **comprehensive information** about the current state of biological potential, as well as developing strategies for its **restoration, improvement, and effective use**, is critically important for the efficient management of economic and agrotechnical processes. This is one of the **key factors** in the **rational management of an enterprise's economic potential**, ensuring **sustainable development**, and **enhancing competitiveness**.

Additionally, when evaluating biological potential, it is essential to consider the following **scientific and practice-based approaches**:

- The **adaptability** of crop varieties and animal breeds to agro-climatic conditions;

- **The level of utilization of genetic potential;**
- **Reproductive characteristics** (i.e., reproduction rate, growth, and productivity indicators);
- **Disease resistance and biological stability;**
- **The degree of implementation of innovative technologies** in the use of biological resources.

Thus, in **agricultural enterprises**, biological potential serves not only as a factor of **production efficiency**, but also as a **strategic resource**. Its scientifically grounded evaluation and management provide a **solid foundation for the enterprise's long-term sustainable operation**.

In the current phase of **globalization** and increasing **competition**, the development of the **market economy** requires **comprehensive approaches** to ensure that agricultural enterprises can establish strong positions in the market. Today, it is becoming **impossible to maintain competitiveness** based solely on traditional production models. Therefore, it is essential for agricultural enterprises to adopt **broad diversification strategies**, meaning they should **not limit their activities to only crop production or livestock farming**, but also expand into **related sectors such as processing, logistics, storage, and marketing**.

In addition, ensuring competitiveness requires the **implementation of innovative technologies**, including **digital agrotechnologies, smart farming systems, and automated monitoring and control tools**, all of which significantly enhance production efficiency. At the same time, attention must be given to **developing the processing sector within the agro-industrial complex**, specifically through **deep processing of agricultural products** to produce **high value-added finished goods**.

On this basis, to ensure the **competitiveness of agricultural enterprises** in a market economy, it is crucial to simultaneously improve their **economic, technological, and organizational capacity**. This includes undertaking **institutional reforms**, introducing **financial support mechanisms**, and developing **agricultural infrastructure strategies**.

As a result of such a **comprehensive approach**, agricultural enterprises can become **sustainable actors capable of supplying competitive products** not only in the **domestic market** but also in **international agrifood markets**.

List of used literature:

1. Yekimov S. et al. Building the potential of an agricultural enterprise //IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. – IOP Publishing, 2021. – T. 677. – №. 2. – C. 022075.

2. Viacheslavna Z. O., Anatolievna O. J. Business activity of agricultural enterprises. Problems and solutions //Азимут научных исследований: экономика и управление. – 2020. – Т. 9. – №. 4 (33). – С. 151-153.
3. Antoshchenkova V. Main elements of the resource potential of agricultural enterprises as the basis of economic and food security //Ekonomichnyy analiz. – 2020. – Т. 30. – №. 3. – С. 291-298.
4. Matyja M. Resources based factors of competitiveness of agricultural enterprises //Management. – 2016. – Т. 20. – №. 1. – С. 368.
5. Samakhavets M. P. Financial Potential of Agricultural Business of the Republic of Belarus in Trade with the Russian Federation //Regionalnaya ekonomika. Yug Rossii. – 2024. – С. 103-114.
6. Абдужаборова М. Хўжалик юритувчи субъектларда молиявий барқарорлик таҳлилини ташкил этиш //Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim. – 2023. – Т. 24. – №. 5. – С. 197-200.
7. Тожибоева Ш., Махкамбоев К., Ташпулатова Г. Иқтисодий салоҳиятнинг айланма маблағлар билан боғлиқ кўрсаткичлари таҳлили //Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim. – 2021. – №. 5. – С. 205-210.
8. Skrynkovskyy R. et al. Improvement of the system of indicators for the efficiency evaluation of the production capacity of industrial enterprises //Технологический аудит и резервы производства. – 2019. – Т. 2. – №. 4 (46). – С. 49-51.
9. Абдувохидов, Акмал, et al. "Қишлоқ хўжалигида иқтисодий ўсиш сифатини аниқлаш ва унинг кўрсаткичлари таҳлили." Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim 23.4 (2022): 16-31.